

Enacting desired futures in the present: Emergent prefiguration in the 2018 Nicaraguan uprising

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Abstract

As global crises intensify and trust in democratic institutions weakens, there has been growing interest in prefigurative politics. Spanning eco-villages to protest movements, prefiguration refers to grassroots efforts to enact desired future social relations through present-day practices. Despite a growing recognition of the relevance of psychological perspectives, empirical research on prefiguration remains scarce. Traditionally understood as an ideologically driven practice, recent protest movements suggest that prefigurative practices can also emerge through struggle. This paper explores the phenomenon of emergent prefiguration through an interview study with 17 participants of the 2018 Nicaraguan uprising. Drawing on a reflexive thematic analysis informed by the elaborated social identity model, we identify four interconnected processes that help explain this emergence: collective identity formation, collective self-objectification, empowering outcomes of collective self-objectification, and prefigurative realization. Through these processes, we suggest that for most participants, the uprising came to be viewed not only as tactical resistance but also as the prefiguration of the society they aspired to see. Advancing the concept of emergent prefiguration, our study calls for a global psychology of collective action that recognises the potential of resistance to both challenge the world as it is and prefigure the world that could be.

Introduction

In recent protest movements – from uprisings across Latin America to the Palestine solidarity encampments – participants are increasingly resisting state structures while embodying, through their practices, the alternatives they wish to see. This approach, known as ‘prefigurative politics’, involves the enactment of desired societal change in the ‘here and now’ of resistance (Raekstad & Gradin, 2020). While prefigurative politics is often understood as an intentional, ideologically-driven practice (Gordon, 2018), examples of recent protest movements suggest it can also emerge through the process of struggle itself. Although social theory links this phenomenon of ‘emergent prefiguration’ (Clarke & Drury, 2025) to the psychological changes experienced by collective action participants, empirical research on how and when this occurs remains scarce.

This study addresses this gap by exploring the emergence of prefigurative collective action during the 2018 Nicaraguan uprising, an event that, *prima facie*, showed evidence of prefigurative politics (e.g. Rocha, 2021) among participants with limited experience of activism. Drawing on in-depth interviews with 17 participants, we develop a new explanatory account of how prefigurative practices emerge through struggle, exploring the underlying psychological mechanisms and processes involved.

To build this account, we draw on key concepts from the elaborated social identity model (ESIM; Drury & Reicher, 2009), such as identity emergence, empowerment, and collective self-objectification (CSO). Our broader goal is to develop a new model of emergent prefiguration – one that can be tested and refined in future research, contributing to both the social psychology of collective action and broader scholarship on prefigurative politics within social movement research.

The turn to prefigurative politics

In the context of overlapping global crises, the institutions that once claimed to provide stability – liberal democracy, the state, international law – now appear increasingly inadequate or actively complicit in sustaining systems of dispossession, imperial violence, and environmental destruction (Brown, 2024; Erakat, 2019). Against this backdrop, activists and communities have increasingly

turned to prefigurative politics—grassroots efforts to enact desired future social relations through present-day social change practices (Fians, 2022). Prefigurative initiatives often bypass appeals to authorities by experimenting with alternative ways of living, organising, and relating—challenging dominant structures while enacting desired alternatives (Dinerstein, 2015).

Although central to anarchist thought since the 19th century (Franks, 2022), prefiguration only gained prominence in social movement studies with the ‘New Left’ movements of the 1960s and 1970s (Boggs, 1977). Academic interest in the prefigurative character of protest movements began to grow during the 1990s, largely sparked by the anti-globalization movement and the increasing prevalence of prefiguration in contentious politics around the world (Monticelli, 2018).

In movements such as the 2011 ‘Arab Spring’, the Latin American uprisings of 2017–2020, and the 2024–25 Palestine solidarity encampments, participants have sought to embody, in their struggles, the kinds of social relations they envision for wider society (Molnárfi & Zito, 2024; Sitrin, 2020; Woods, 2022). Through their resistance, protesters transformed occupied spaces into sites where ideals of equality and democracy were not only advocated but *enacted* through everyday practices. Critical of capitalism, the state, and centralised power, participants in these movements embraced direct democracy, horizontality, and autonomy (Sahin, 2024), *prefiguring* the kind of egalitarian, participatory, and autonomous societies they aspired to see.

Prefiguration has traditionally been understood as a deliberate, ideologically driven practice (Gordon, 2018). However, in recent prefigurative protest movements, groups do not appear to start out with radical social change aims; rather, prefigurative understandings and practices seem to emerge ‘spontaneously’ through the unfolding dynamics of the struggle itself (Sitrin, 2020). This phenomenon – known as ‘emergent prefigurative politics’ (Clarke & Drury, 2025) – raises important questions for social psychology: How might the collective experience of resistance contribute to the enactment of prefigurative practices? And under what conditions of struggle do participants begin to understand their actions, not merely as oppositional, but as also building the futures they seek?

Research on prefigurative politics

Despite the growing relevance of prefigurative politics in contemporary movements, its study remains fragmented within social movement and collective action research. Authors have noted an absence of explanatory frameworks in psychology (Trott, 2016) and sociology (Monticelli, 2018), and a lack of attention to prefigurative movements across the Global South (Sitrin, 2020). As a result, emergent prefiguration has yet to be systematically explored in social movement scholarship.

In the absence of significant empirical research, social theory has provided some insights into how prefiguration might emerge through struggle. Marxist theorists have suggested that collective struggle fosters psychological changes in participants, leading to the development of new beliefs and capacities (Raekstad, 2018). For example, Raekstad (2015) argues that while participants may initially adopt new practices for strategic reasons, sustained engagement can reshape their understanding of their actions, leading them to value the practices as ‘ends in themselves’.

While Marxist accounts of prefiguration often draw on psychological concepts (e.g., consciousness), they do not provide detailed explanations. Yet empirical psychological studies on prefiguration remain scarce, with a recent systematic review identifying only 20 published studies in the field (Clarke & Drury, 2025). This gap is particularly striking given that, over the years, commentators have increasingly highlighted the relevance of psychological inquiry to questions about how prefigurative politics emerges, develops, and impacts participants (Cornish et al., 2016; Malherbe, 2023; Trott, 2016).

Despite the limited research, existing psychological studies offer some support for social theory’s emphasis on psychological change (e.g., empowerment) in the emergence of prefiguration through struggle (see Clarke & Drury, 2025, for a review). However, there remains a lack of in-depth explanatory accounts detailing the psychological mechanisms driving this process. Moreover, very few studies have explored these dynamics in the context of uprisings and protest movements, despite their significance as sites for exploring political and psychological change.

Psychological change through collective action – the emergence of prefigurative action?

While prefiguration has not been a primary focus in social psychology, researchers have examined the psychological transformations experienced by participants of collective action for some time (e.g., Drury & Reicher, 2000; Vestergren & Acar, 2023). One particularly fruitful framework for understanding emergent prefiguration is the elaborated social identity model (ESIM; Drury & Reicher, 2009), which focuses on the dynamic process through which collective identities emerge and evolve during the course of a struggle. Unlike most social psychological models of collective action, which focus on static antecedents (e.g., SIMCA; van Zomeren et al., 2008), ESIM highlights the context-specific and emergent nature of collective action – including how participation itself can lead to transformative shifts in identity and intentions, with participants coming to embrace new understandings about self, politics, and possibilities for change (Drury & Reicher, 2009; Vestergren et al., 2018).

This framework would appear to be well-suited to exploring the emergence of prefiguration, where novel understandings and practices are thought to arise through the unfolding dynamics of struggle (Clarke & Drury, 2025; Trott, 2016). Although a few empirical studies of prefiguration have fruitfully incorporated some ESIM concepts (Acar & Ulug, 2016; Mao et al., 2021), no research has yet drawn on its insights to explore the emergence of prefigurative collective action.

The present study

To address these gaps in the literature, this study examines the emergence of prefigurative politics in the 2018 Nicaraguan uprising through in-depth interviews with 17 participants. Specifically, we seek to develop an explanatory account by identifying the psychological mechanisms and processes that may have facilitated this emergence process.

As in other postmillennial uprisings, commentators have highlighted the prefigurative character of the Nicaraguan context, particularly in the roadblocks and self-organised protest groups where protesters reportedly enacted horizontality, mutual-aid, and autonomy in their months-long challenge against the Nicaraguan government (Bran Aragon & Goett, 2020; Rocha, 2021).

The Nicaraguan uprising offers a valuable setting for examining the ‘spontaneous’ emergence of prefigurative practices. With the government having co-opted or severely weakened existing social movements, traditional movement structures could not function effectively. As a result, protesters rapidly created new, decentralised self-organised groups to resist the brutally repressive state (Rocha, 2021).

To guide our analysis, we explore whether key ESIM processes – such as identity emergence and empowerment – can help explain how collective resistance evolved into prefigurative collective action. Through this case study, we ask: Did participants experience the uprising in prefigurative terms? If so, how did resistance practices – initially rooted in opposition to the government – come to be understood in these terms? In addressing these questions, we aim to develop an explanatory model to be tested and refined in future research. More broadly, we consider how emergent prefiguration challenges dominant understandings of collective action, and we position our study as contributing to growing efforts to develop a more global and dynamic psychology of collective action.

Methods

Participants

We recruited seventeen participants (9 women, 8 men) through personal contacts and snowball sampling. Thirteen interviews were conducted in 2022, and five additional interviews – conducted by the first author in 2019 with eligible participants – were also included. One person was interviewed in both periods. Participants were selected based on their involvement in key sites of resistance during the 2018 uprising, including roadblocks (7), self-organized protest groups (7), and university occupations (3). In line with our focus on emergent prefiguration, we prioritised recruiting individuals with limited prior activist experience to increase the likelihood that prefigurative understandings developed through the uprising itself, rather than reflecting pre-existing ideological commitments. Participants ranged in age from 16 to 33; most were university students, recent graduates, or young professionals navigating a context marked by corruption and limited opportunities. They were based in five regions: Managua (9), Carazo (4), Masaya (2), Estelí (1), León (1). All took on a range of roles supporting the movement: organizing medical care and community kitchens, managing logistics and security, guarding roadblocks, coordinating mass mobilizations, and engaging in outreach and media work to build local and international support.

Interview schedule and procedure

Semi-structured interviews were conducted using a schedule organised into four sections, informed by the ESIM: (1) Perceptions of the political context prior to the uprising (e.g., “How did you view the political situation before the protests?”); (2) Experiences in roadblocks, occupations, and self-organised protest groups (e.g., “Tell me about your participation in the roadblocks/occupations/protest groups?”); (3) The impact of state repression on perceptions of authorities, protester identity, and intra-group relations (e.g., “How did state repression affect your attitudes toward the government and the police?”); (4) Empowerment processes (e.g., “How did the sense of what you could achieve as a movement change as the uprising unfolded?”). All interviews followed this ESIM-informed structure; only the most recent schedule included additional prompts

specifically focused on prefiguration. (“How did these experiences affect your sense of what national politics might be like?”).

Interviews were conducted by the first author in Spanish and ranged from 50 to 120 minutes, taking place either in person or remotely via Microsoft Teams. With participants’ consent, interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and then anonymised during transcription.

Data analysis

We conducted a reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019) of the interview transcripts, drawing on insights from ESIM. Transcripts were first read and re-read to ensure immersion in the data. Initial coding was inductive, identifying salient features of participants’ accounts, but interpretation was informed by key concepts from ESIM, particularly identity emergence, empowerment, and CSO. Codes were then iteratively developed and organised into preliminary themes, through a recursive process of moving between codes, data extracts, and developing thematic structures. Throughout the analysis, translated excerpts were shared with the second author, who provided feedback on code definition. Themes were developed collaboratively, attending closely to participants’ specific utterances and understandings, using theoretical concepts as a framework for interpreting patterns across the data. The raw data are not publicly available due to the sensitive nature of the research, the associated risks to participants, and the lack of consent for data sharing in repositories.

Contextual overview of the uprising

In April 2018, Nicaragua experienced one of the most significant uprisings in its recent history. What began as a protest against a controversial government reform to the social security system rapidly escalated, driven by repression and broader grievances against the increasingly authoritarian rule of President Daniel Ortega. The initial protest on April 18th was met with brutal violence. While the police stood by, pro-government mobs armed with sticks and metal tubes brutally attacked protesters, forcibly suppressing demonstrations in two Nicaraguan cities (Confidential, 2018). Footage of the unprovoked attack spread rapidly on social media, fuelling widespread outrage at the deliberate targeting of peaceful demonstrators -- which included elderly pensioners -- and the state's perceived complicity in the attack. The next day, fuelled by this anger, protests rapidly intensified with protests spreading to at least nine cities (The Guardian, 2018)

The government responded with brutal force to suppress the demonstrations; within days, over 30 protesters had been killed by paramilitary forces and the police (Associated Press, 2018). Despite the withdrawal of the proposed social security reform on April 21st, protests persisted daily, driven by anger over the repression and accumulated grievances. Over the previous decade, Ortega had systematically concentrated its power, dismantled democratic institutions, restricted independent media, and suppressed opposition groups.

Roadblocks became central to the nationwide movement, with protesters setting up barricades in every major city of the country. In July, at the height of the uprising, approximately 600 roadblocks had been set up nationwide, significantly disrupting economic activity (Cabrales, 2019)

With roadblocks, mass demonstrations and national strikes, the movement forced a brief negotiation process. However, after failed attempts, the government launched a nationwide "clean up" operation, dismantling all roadblocks, imprisoning hundreds of protesters on charges of terrorism, and introducing new legislation that effectively criminalised protest (Stirling Hill, 2019).

International human rights organizations, including the Inter American Commission on Human Rights and Amnesty International, condemned the Nicaraguan government's lethal response.

Reports (e.g., Amnesty International, 2018) detailed the use of high-calibre live ammunition, extrajudicial killings, and torture as part of a systematic strategy to quash opposition, resulting in over 300 deaths in just three months. Despite these widespread condemnations, the Ortega regime dismissed the protests as a CIA-sponsored coup (Associated Press, 2024) and remains in power.

Analysis

Across the interviews, most participants framed their resistance in prefigurative terms, describing it as a struggle that evolved beyond mere opposition to the Ortega regime. Six predominantly described their practices as already embodying the changes they wished to see in Nicaragua ('living the future'), while nine mainly emphasized aligning means with future political ends ('be the change you want to see'). Two participants provided no evidence of prefigurative understandings, focusing instead on regime change and surviving state repression. Despite these variations, most participants described experiences in which they sought not only to demand change but, to some extent, enact what they aspired that change to look like. In the following, we propose an explanatory account to outline how these prefigurative understandings and practices emerged, organised into four themes: (1) Collective identity formation; (2) Collective self-objectification through resistance practices; (3) Empowering outcomes of collective self-objectification; (4) Prefigurative realization.

Theme 1: Collective identity formation

This theme explores how, in line with ESIM, an attack experienced as both indiscriminate and illegitimate catalysed the formation of a unified and oppositional collective identity and how the 'self-convened protester' emerged as the movement's prototypical member.

1.1. Repression as catalyst

All interviewees, whether present at one of the initial protests or who joined later, described these events as a turning point. The indiscriminate attack by pro-government mobs – targeting even the elderly and journalists – was widely seen as proof that “no one was safe”, creating a sense of common fate:

There was a sense that if the government allowed that with the elderly, who obviously weren't doing anything criminal, then no one was safe. It's much harder to imagine an old person throwing rocks or attacking anyone (...) I think we all saw our grandparents there... (Sofia, roadblock participant, Estelí)

Because repression targeted peaceful protesters rather than “criminal acts”, many participants felt they, too, could have been targeted. This shared vulnerability fostered a broad, inclusive self-categorization among people who had not previously seen themselves as politically aligned. As one participant, who joined the next day, recalled:

As a feminist, I have a hard time with nationalisms, because I know that I live in a patriarchal country, but something in me made me want to wear a flag at the time. There was like a truce (...) It was what united us, the only thing that united us all – to say: ‘We are Nicaragua and we don't want to be repressed!’ (Sofia, roadblock participant, Estelí)

Many described this emerging identity as suspending boundaries, uniting people from different backgrounds under a superordinate national category. Thus, while interviewees reported joining protests in five cities on the second day, these were not isolated demonstrations, but the beginning of a coordinated, nationwide movement.

The first protest was widely described as a legitimate exercise of democratic rights, shaping participants’ expectations that the police would protect citizens. The combination of mob violence and police complicity was, thus, viewed as an extreme violation of those rights:

Just as we arrived, we saw an old man covered in blood (...) and a journalist who had just had his head split open (...) What shocked me, not so much anymore, was the fact that the police seemed to be protecting the mobs... even though they saw the kinds of hand-made weapons they had, they weren’t doing anything to stop them (Julia, student protest group, Managua)

The government’s perceived responsibility for the attack fuelled a generalised perception of the authorities’ illegitimacy. Several interviewees described moments of realization where this shift in understanding was linked to a more radical sense of identity as protesters:

Once you see that the state is cynically using institutional resources [the police] to attack the freedoms of a sector of the population [people who dissent], there is no turning back! When you realise that the force that is there to protect you is the one that will destroy you, you have to challenge them (Ana, student protest group, Managua)

As state forces were no longer seen as neutral but as instruments of repression, participants frequently expressed they now felt compelled to resist rather than respect their authority.

1.2 “Self-convened” protester as prototypical group member

In line with self-categorization theory (Turner et al., 1987), this subtheme unpacks the cognitive (‘who we are’) and strategic (‘how we sustain resistance’) processes underlying the emergence of this prototypical identity.

1.2.1 ‘Who we are’

A recurring theme across participants’ accounts was the process of identity-differentiation, as protesters defined themselves in opposition to the government across a number of qualities. For example:

We would talk about the importance of not being like them [the government], we felt a need to mark a difference in how we acted compared to them. We kept telling ourselves ‘We are not like them, we are not going to act like them. We are not going to respond with the same violence as them,’ because that would make us no different from them (Maya, student protest group, Managua)

This illustrates how non-violence, for nearly all interviewees, became a defining feature that distinguished the movement from its repressive enemy. Participants’ early efforts to define themselves against government repression evolved alongside a broader disillusionment with national politics, laying the foundations for the emergence of the “self-convened protester” concept. As one participant explained:

We were self-convened because we had to start from scratch (...) everything was dirty, everything was stained: with impunity, with corruption, with political pacts, with electoral frauds, with misuse of state resources... (Ernesto, university occupation, Managua)

Rejecting traditional political actors, most participants spoke of having no place within existing structures. As a counter-point, the ‘self-convened protester’ – a term all interviewees

identified with – emerged as the prototypical group member, grounded in autonomy from traditional political channels and participation through personal conviction. This emphasis on autonomy made the movement open to all aggrieved citizens, making hierarchies difficult to justify. All interviewees therefore emphasised horizontality as a defining feature of the movement:

We had lots of utopian ideas of what our student movement should be to try to avoid repeating historical patterns [that the government was repeating]. And we tried to organise ourselves in groups too and not have a leader to avoid a vertical hierarchy. (Maya, student protest group, Managua)

1.2.2 Strategic processes

With existing movements seen as compromised or absent, framing the movement as ‘self-convened’ enabled resistance without formal structures, shielded it from accusations of co-optation, and resonated with widespread dissatisfaction with national politics. One participant, who spoke of how opposition political leaders were rebuffed at protests, explained:

We were there as Nicaragua [in a march on the third day of protests], there were no political flags there. The only flag was the blue and white of our country. (Sofia, roadblock participant, Estelí)

Thus, for most participants, the movement drew power from being “self-convened”, representing unity around collective grievances and interest, rather than personal or political agendas:

By being self-convened, without acronyms, without parties, without anything, just with our own aspirations, so to speak... desires for them [the government] to stand down, we were all united and acting as one (Fernando, university occupation, Managua)

Non-violence, similarly, was not only a principle but a pragmatic stance. One participant eloquently highlighted this dual role:

The strategy of non-violence was mainly about the fact that non-violence as a principle was important to us, but it is also very easy to delegitimise you if you respond and react to provocations. So, I think it was partly about being consistent with what we were building [as an uprising] and about not letting [protester] violence distract from the real actions that were happening [state repression] (Maya, student protest group, Managua)

This highlights how commitment to non-violence was both principled and tactical – crucial for maintaining legitimacy and public support.

Theme 2: Collective self-objectification through resistance practices

This theme describes how the uprising involved not only the formation of a new collective identity but also the enactment of this identity through resistance practices. The lack of established organizational structures created a context where the emerging collective identity was crucial in guiding the nature of collective action. By structuring their resistance around this newfound identity, participants experienced their values in action in ways not possible in ordinary life – a process termed collective self-objectification (CSO; Drury & Reicher, 2009).

Across interviews, participants frequently described enacting their emerging collective identity through participation in roadblocks, protest spaces, and self-organised protest groups. While roadblocks were initially set up for strategic purposes – to block state forces, protect communities from looting, and signal dissent – most interviewees came to view them as spaces where shared values were practised. The following account vividly illustrates this dual role:

(...) While we were guarding the roadblock, it was like feeling owners of the country. And so, owners of our lives (...) By taking the streets and sitting there, even with all the fears that we had and everything, especially when there were warnings [of police attacks], right? (...) I mean, it was also like we were finding new ways of coexisting with one another, of being able to disagree with another (...). If we had decided that we were just randomly meeting every Sunday in the street to chat, it would have some value, but this had so much more value

because we were there also stopping traffic. We were sending a message to Ortega. (Sofia, roadblock participant, Estelí)

Amidst the threat of lethal repression, setting up and guarding roadblocks was experienced as a powerful assertion of autonomy, agency, and dignity – enacting the right to be heard, to act collectively, and to relate on their own terms. In the absence of formal leadership or organizational structures, most participants described these spaces as functioning through shared responsibility and horizontal decision-making. Echoing this, several described the roadblocks as “mini-democracies”, “mini-governments”, and “mini-societies” – terms that suggest these autonomous spaces became, for many, experiments in participatory self-organization, in clear contrast to the authoritarianism they were opposing.

Beyond roadblocks, other practices also enabled the enactment of shared values. One example was the toppling of “Steel Trees” – state monuments viewed as symbols of government excess amid economic hardship and widespread deforestation. For many, this widely supported action took on deeper meaning:

It wasn't just the toppling, there was a whole like cultural performance that went with it. There was music, there was singing, there was dancing, there were slogans, it was like a collective hug. It wasn't just a simple toppling and for me that was really beautiful (...) It wasn't just about the fall; it was the cultural event that accompanied the fall (...) We built a sort of offering – we mounted crosses, we brought flowers, and we printed photos of the victims (...) We planted trees too, so that they'd grow where the “Steel Tree” had fallen. We started planting trees and we would water them in the afternoon (...). It was like creating something new where the old was... letting the new flourish. (Yara, student protest group, Managua)

The participant frames the action not as destruction, but as a meaningful cultural event that combined collective expression, mourning, and renewal. Through music, offerings, and the planting

of trees, she and others involved in the action enacted shared values of autonomy, collective care, and environmental responsibility.

Theme 3: Empowering outcomes of collective self-objectification

This theme describes how collective self-objectification during the uprising was empowering for participants and transformative in reshaping their understandings of themselves, their actions, and the possibilities of change. Specifically, we identified two CSO-related outcomes: (1) increased feasibility of alternative social relations; and (2) increased desirability of alternative social relations.

3.1 Increased feasibility of alternative social relations

In reflecting on the period before the uprising, all participants spoke of a pervasive hopelessness – a sense that meaningful social change was impossible under the Ortega regime’s dominance and in the absence of credible alternatives. As one participant recalled:

Yeah, all of us young people were a bit resigned [about politics] (...) I would say that I wasn't very interested in politics (...) I remember I didn't vote in the 2014 or 2015 elections... at the time I was thinking: what for? One vote won't make a difference. What for? I already know they're going to be stolen. What for? I know that they'll throw the ballots away and declare the same winners anyway (Jessica, student movement, Managua)

While resignation was widespread, most interviewees described their participation in the uprising as fundamentally shifting their sense of what was politically *possible* – many of which seemed tied to the process of collectively organizing and sustaining such a historic resistance effort. For example:

In terms of politics, we're full of negative ideas: 'all governments are useless', 'they're all the same'... so if we don't have positive references, how can we imagine alternatives? But I don't know how to express just how well-organized our roadblock was... and all of this came from people saying, 'I have knowledge in this area', 'I have knowledge in this other area,', 'we can coordinate guard duty', and so on. And, to see all of this working, I feel like it subconsciously

cleans up all of the bad examples we've lived through the years (Victoria, Roadblock participant, Managua).

Witnessing the roadblock functioning effectively – through people voluntarily contributing skills, making decisions collectively, and solving problems together – challenged prior political cynicism and provided a new – more hopeful – reference point. Similar accounts were particularly common when participants discussed the peak of the uprising, during May and June, when roadblocks had paralysed much of the country and police were confined to their headquarters in several cities (Klein et al., 2022). In this context, many participants described how the scale of the resistance, the effectiveness of the roadblocks, and the government's inability to re-impose control contributed to the widely shared belief that the uprising was going to overthrow the regime. As one participant noted:

For me, it got to the point where we could say 'you don't govern us; we don't recognise the government of Ortega'. We were the government; us, the people. We showed this when flooding the streets one day [through mass marches] and leaving them completely empty the next [through national strikes]. That for me was one of the most impressive things – it was iconic, I don't think I'll ever forget that feeling (Gabriela, student protest group, León)

When asked about the impact of these experiences, she elaborated:

It made me think that other forms of government were possible – no, not forms of government, but other ways of doing politics. If we are making the decisions, we can transform our country ourselves (...) I think we achieved a cultural change with the non-violence approach, for example.

The participant describes not only resisting the regime but doing so in a way that led her to reimagine politics itself. Building a powerful movement aligned with values like autonomy and non-violence – and seeing those values work in practice – seemed to validate the possibility of doing things on their own terms. In this example, taking part in mass, self-organised marches and national strikes offered tangible evidence that the movement's value-driven collective practice could be sustained and potentially scaled beyond isolated acts of protest.

For some, this realization of new social possibilities was tied to the structures built to sustain resistance. At roadblocks and occupied universities, protesters built makeshift medical posts, community kitchens, and security and waste disposal systems – often maintained for weeks without formal leadership. Several participants spoke of the transformative experience of organising these spaces to meet urgent resistance and communal needs:

Many at our roadblock had studied or practiced medicine, so we set up a makeshift medical post. And, as I mentioned before, three babies were born there! The city was blockaded [by protester roadblocks] making access to the hospital difficult (...) and some hospitals refused to treat protesters on government orders (...) A few times people called us because they couldn't reach the hospital, so we mobilised doctors on motorbikes for house visits (...) It was an amazing experience (...) we were building like a mini-government... or what a government could be like if it looked after the community (...) Throughout the city, people were sick of the stench of the rubbish piling up in their homes because everything was paralysed. So, some young guys got hold of a rubbish truck and went around collecting rubbish, shouting 'Take out your rubbish!'. We weren't a government, we weren't trying to replace the government, but we were trying to meet the needs of the community that it wasn't responding to. (Lucas, roadblock participant, Carazo)

In the absence of state intervention, these protesters organised essential services themselves – not to replicate the government, but to meet the needs it was neglecting, and to do so on fundamentally different terms. For this participant, and others in this subset, shaping key aspects of everyday life – from health care to sanitation – was a deeply empowering experience. These efforts not only sustained resistance; they also offered tangible evidence that their collective practice – grounded in values of autonomy, community, and self-governance – could serve as the basis for organising social life.

Thus, through collective self-objectification, participants were not only resisting an oppressive order but discovering their collective capacity to organize and sustain an alternative one. In a context of widespread resignation and fatalism, this represented the profound realization that the existing,

oppressive world was not inevitable, and that a new one built on their own terms might just be feasible.

3.2 Increased desirability of alternative social relations

All interviewees spoke about the Ortega government's creeping authoritarianism and how, over time, it came to dictate even the most basic aspects of everyday life. For example:

At universities, scholarships depended on your political allegiances (...) All the country's institutions were controlled by the regime. From everything to requesting your birth certificate or ID, having a [governing] party militant card helped a lot. It was the same for state jobs. In hospitals, even medical attention depended on it. I'm talking about things that should be citizen rights, which were here tied to supporting the regime. Living under these conditions was degrading (...) it was a humiliating context. (Ernesto, university occupation, Managua)

This account highlights not only the politicization of civil and social institutions, but also the emotional toll of navigating a system in which basic rights and services were contingent on political loyalty. Across interviews, participants stressed how this context eroded their sense of agency, autonomy, and dignity, creating a climate of fear and mistrust that isolated people from one another.

By contrast, most interviewees described roadblocks, occupations, and protest spaces as important sites where they regained, at least temporarily, the sense of autonomy, dignity, and community that had long been undermined. While not all made direct comparisons, the contrast was often evident in their descriptions about life before and during the uprising. Some articulated this shift explicitly. For example, describing a large protest march, one interviewee reflected:

I think together what we were fighting for was like the right to life... life in all its expressions. To live means being able to express yourself freely; you can't conceive of a life if you can't express yourself freely, or worse, if they kill you for it (...) I remember a march where we went through the whole town. We started at [school] and more and more people joined in... first it was too sunny, then it rained, and we got wet, then we dried off, then it rained again. But we didn't care... we were enjoying something we hadn't realised how much

we needed. To be able to come out onto the streets and say: ‘This street is mine. I have the right to express myself, and I don’t want you to kill me’. (Sofia, roadblock-participant, Estelí)

Here, the participant reflects on how the march disrupted the enforced silence that had come to define everyday life. Reclaiming the streets collectively exposed just how profoundly the right to speak and act publicly had been denied – and how exhilarating it felt to regain them. Through collective defiance, previously suppressed values were not just demanded, but materialised: dignity, freedom, and a sense of collective agency. A few participants reflected on the idea of extending these kinds of fulfilling experiences into wider society:

[At a roadblock] (...) we started to wonder why we couldn’t maintain things like this the whole time, of achieving this same sense of unity and fraternity all the time, of being all united, working for the same objectives. (...) I would talk to different people about it; about how beautiful it would be if we could achieve this same sense of community and sense of togetherness all the time (...) We would say ‘wow, isn’t it amazing what we’re building, isn’t it beautiful!’. And I’m telling you, despite all the struggles I’ve had to continue dealing with as a political refugee, I still wouldn’t change anything about what I did (Xochitl, roadblock participant, Carazo).

The participant doesn’t just reflect on what she gained through resisting – experiences of unity, fraternity, and community – but expresses a desire to carry these ways of relating into the future. Like others, her account suggests that participation revealed not only the feasibility of alternative social relations, but also their *desirability* – offering a glimpse of what it meant to organise social life – not on the regime’s terms, but on their own. For her, these experiences – despite the uprising’s failure – were powerful enough to make her later struggles worthwhile.

Theme 4: Prefigurative realization

This final theme traces how the empowering outcomes of collective identity enactment through resistance led most participants to view their actions not only as oppositional but as a partial enactment of the society they aspired to build. This shift was evidenced in two distinct ways: six

mainly framed their involvement as ‘living the future through the uprising’, while nine mainly adopted a “be the change you want to see’ orientation – though in some cases these distinctions were not clear-cut and a few accounts incorporated elements of both.

Initially, participants saw their resistance as a response to government repression and long-standing grievances. However, as the struggle unfolded, their involvement offered empowering experiences that reshaped their beliefs about the possibility and desirability of alternative social relations. In most accounts, these experiences were linked to a deeper realization: their resistance was no longer just about opposing an oppressive present but, increasingly, about enacting elements of a future society. The first orientation – ‘living the future through the uprising’ – is powerfully illustrated in the following extract:

There was a huge contrast between the government and us. As opposed to the government, we managed to build a mini-democracy at our roadblock, and I feel that was because we developed true leadership and were able to work together; because, when people organise themselves by asking people who wants to do what, or who has certain knowledge they can contribute, that’s delegating things rather than imposing, right? I came to experience our roadblock as an example of what a future Nicaragua could be like (Victoria, roadblock participant, Masaya.)

The participant reflects on how organizing the roadblock took on broader significance. What began as a tactic evolved into an effective collective practice based on voluntary participation, knowledge-sharing, and horizontal decision-making – enacting values of direct action, autonomy, and horizontality. By calling the roadblock a “mini-democracy” and “an example of what a future Nicaragua could be like”, she articulates a clear prefigurative realization: a shift to viewing the roadblock as a working model for the more participatory and democratic society she hoped to see.

The second orientation – ‘be the change you want to see’ – was evident in accounts that stressed the need to embody the movement’s values in their everyday practices. For example:

For me, April became one of the most genuine efforts to break the cycle of our history... a cycle marked by political violence, corruption, inequality, fear, precariousness, machismo, authoritarianism. It became an attempt, by a generation, to go beyond resignation and recognise that real change had to come from the ground up, starting with our own actions (...)

For me, the uprising became about so much more than just the removal of a dictator (...).

(Maya, student protest group, Managua)

Here, the participant frames the uprising not simply as a demand for regime change, but as an effort to break from entrenched patterns of violence, corruption, and authoritarianism that had long shaped Nicaraguan life. Like others in this subset, she emphasises that transformation had to begin through their own actions. This commitment to embodying their ideals in practice suggests the emergence of a generative approach to resistance: an understanding that the desired future could only be achieved by enacting it through the struggle itself. In this way, non-violence, horizontality, or other practices that became key to the movement were not just enactments of protester identity but attempts to prefigure the political culture they aspired to create.

These two accounts illustrate distinct but complementary ways in which participants' shift towards prefigurative action was expressed. Whether through experiencing the collective practices of the uprising as tangible examples of their desired future society, or through deliberately embodying the movement's core values in their everyday actions, both represent a shift beyond mere oppositional resistance. Instead, their participation came to be understood as an attempt to enact the kind of society they aspired to see.

Negative cases

Two participants did not express any prefigurative understandings. Although they participated in the roadblocks and university occupations that others found empowering, neither articulated a resulting shift in their beliefs about social change. Instead, their accounts centred on strategic concerns, disillusionment with the uprising's eventual outcome, and the trauma of losing friends to repression. Practices were described instrumentally – as means of protection or resistance – rather than

as transformative. One participant, unlike others who came to see non-violence as a way of aligning means with future political visions, stressed the tactical necessity of violence:

[I felt] that we needed weapons and that we all needed to go to El Carmen [the Presidential Residence]... and if some of us had to die, so be it, but we had to get these people out. In the end, these processes always leave victims. Maybe there would have been a lot in this case, but I think what the national dialogue did was give the dictatorship more time and allow Nicaraguans to continue dying slowly every day (Alex, university occupation, Managua)

The other participant who helped organise a major roadblock recalled acts of mutual aid and solidarity, but did not describe them as empowering. When asked whether her participation changed her views about politics, she replied:

At that moment, all you were thinking about was how to protect what you had... you didn't have time to overthink things. (Karen, roadblock participant, Carazo)

Though she later described aspects of the roadblocks as 'beautiful', her reflection was marked by grief following the loss of friends during the repression:

(...) there were beautiful moments, emotional moments, moments of solidarity...moments worth remembering, moments you'd want to frame. But there were others that bring a lot of pain. (...) It was a traumatic process (...) Right now, I'm trying to remember the beautiful moments, but it's really hard...there's so much pain, so much guilt as well.

Unlike others who described their experiences as transformative, these two accounts focused on the aftermath, expressing pain, disappointment, and frustration rather than empowerment or shifts in social change beliefs.

Discussion

This study explored participants' experiences of the 2018 Nicaraguan uprising as a potential case of emergent prefigurative politics, drawing on concepts from the ESIM to explain how individuals came to understand their collective action practices in prefigurative terms. In the discussion that follows, we first situate our findings within the sparse literature on prefigurative politics, then propose a tentative, ESIM-informed model of how collective struggle can evolve into prefigurative action, before reflecting on the broader implications of our study for understanding the psychology of collective action.

Our analysis suggests that through their involvement in roadblocks, university occupations, and self-organised protest groups, most interviewees came to experience their resistance as more than tactical opposition – often framing it in profoundly prefigurative terms. These findings – based on interviews with protesters with limited prior activist experience – suggest that this shift in understanding was neither preplanned nor guided by a fixed blueprint, but emerged over the course of the struggle, shaped by the empowering experiences made possible through collective action.

However, not all participants described such transformations. Two accounts centred more on repression, loss, and tactical concerns than on empowerment or changed understandings of social change. Whether these protesters never experienced prefigurative understandings, or whether such experiences were later overshadowed by trauma and the uprising's outcome, remains unclear. Rather than offer definitive claims, these findings highlight the complexity of how participants make sense of collective action, particularly in the aftermath of brutal repression, profound loss, and disillusionment.

Contributions to the psychology of prefiguration

Our study responds to the growing recognition of the need to examine the psychology of prefiguration, alongside a relative lack of empirical research in this area (Clarke & Drury, 2025; Trott, 2016). We contribute to the sparse and fragmented literature by offering a detailed analysis of a case where prefigurative practices emerged through struggle. By examining the Nicaraguan uprising, a context that exhibited *prima facie* evidence of the spontaneous adoption of prefigurative practices

(eg., Rocha, 2021), we provide an explanatory account identifying key psychological mechanisms that help explain this transformation.

While existing studies had pointed to the role of psychological changes experienced by participants (e.g., empowerment), few have developed detailed explanatory accounts (cf. Sales et al., 2020). Furthermore, our study addresses the lack of research on protest movements and uprisings in the literature, crucial sites to explore the emergence of new forms of political action due to their often-spontaneous nature.

Although grounded in social psychological concepts, our analysis aligns closely with Marxist accounts of prefiguration (e.g., Raekstad, 2015), which emphasise struggle as psychologically transformative, sometimes leading participants to recognise initially pragmatic practices as elements of the society they aspire to build (Raekstad, 2015). Our findings suggest that social psychology – and ESIM in particular – may be able to provide the psychological basis for these accounts.

Towards a tentative model of emergent prefiguration

Drawing on our findings, we suggest a tentative explanatory model integrating four interconnected psychological processes: 1) collective identity formation; 2) collective self-objectification; 3) empowering outcomes of collective self-objectification; 4) prefigurative realization.

Collective identity formation

At the outset of a struggle, individuals may adopt collective practices (e.g., horizontality) based on immediate resistance needs (e.g., ensuring coordinated action) – not as arbitrary acts, but as meaningful expressions of an emerging collective identity. This sense of “we-ness” sets boundaries and norms for action, while remaining open to renegotiation by group members (Reicher et al., 2010).

Collective self-objectification

As resistance unfolds, resistance practices – like organizing roadblocks – can both meet immediate tactical needs and serve to *materialise* the group’s emerging collective identity and values

(e.g., autonomy). Through these actions, participants are able to experience abstract ideals as tangible, lived realities.

Empowering outcomes of collective self-objectification

As Drury and Reicher (2009) have argued, this collective self-objectification can be profoundly empowering, fundamentally altering participants' beliefs about themselves, their actions, and the possibilities of social change. Through CSO, people can not only challenge a relationship of domination; they may also experience a transformed sense of what is possible, where alternative ways of organizing social life – once unthinkable – can be experienced as genuinely *feasible* features of the world. In a world typically structured by powerful out-groups, experiencing a world aligned with collective self-definitions can be thrilling (Drury & Reicher, 2009). Thus, the emotionally fulfilling experiences generated by structuring resistance spaces around usually suppressed values can also trigger or reinforce the *desirability* of such a world.

Prefigurative realization

Through these combined mechanisms – where one's collective practice and values have proved themselves to be both effective (*feasibility*) and fulfilling (*desirability*) – there emerges a conviction to fight for a world built on such terms. It is this, we argue, that can fuel a realization of one's collective practice as not merely a tool for resistance, but over time, as an enactment or embodiment of that very world.

Given ESIM's dynamic conceptualization of the relationship between identity and empowerment – where identity both precedes and is reshaped by empowered action – we do not suggest that these processes follow a strictly linear path. Instead, we emphasise their recursive and overlapping nature, where a prefigurative realization emerges through ongoing cycles of struggle, transformation, and identity redefinition. Rather than unfolding sequentially, identity formation, enactment, and empowerment can mutually shape and reinforce each other (see figure 1).

This raises the possibility – grounded in theory, though not fully demonstrated by our data – that prefigurative practices may become part of an ongoing recursive cycle, in which identity, action,

and empowerment co-evolve through continued engagement. Although our study captures only a single phase of what may be a more extensive process, it offers a foundation for future work exploring not only the origins, but also the development and continuity of prefigurative politics over time.

Figure 1. Tentative ESIM-based model of the emergence of prefigurative collective action

Strengths, Limitations and future research

The Nicaraguan 2018 uprising provides a valuable case for exploring the emergence of prefigurative practices and the role of social psychological processes, considering its spontaneous nature and the minimal prior activist experience of most interviewees. A key strength of the study is that the concept of prefiguration was never introduced during the interviews; instead, participants themselves articulated understandings and practices that align with prefigurative politics.

However, the single-case design limits the transferability of findings to other socio-historical contexts. Further research, especially comparative case studies, is needed to assess whether and how these processes unfold across different sociopolitical settings. While our findings are grounded in the spontaneous, largely unstructured context of the Nicaraguan uprising, future research could explore the relevance of our model across other protest movements, over more sustained periods, and in more structured forms of collective action. Future studies could examine whether the recursive processes identified here also shape the development and consolidation of prefigurative practices in other movements.

A further limitation is the study's reliance on retrospective accounts, collected either two or four years after the uprising. These accounts are susceptible to hindsight bias and post-hoc rationalization. We sought to mitigate this by probing for concrete examples and encouraging participants to review diaries and social media accounts beforehand.

Ideally, a longitudinal design tracking participants' evolving understandings in real time would provide more rigorous evidence. However, this approach is extremely difficult for such topics: uprisings are unpredictable, and research in repressive contexts raises major ethical and practical challenges in terms of risk, recruitment, and participant retention.

Emergent prefiguration and the psychology of collective action

Beyond its empirical contributions to the literature on prefigurative politics, our study raises broader questions about how psychology understands the relationship between collective action and social change – which we turn to in this final section. A growing strand of recent research on collective action has turned to ‘utopian thinking’ – examining how imagined future societies can shape motivation to participate in social change efforts (e.g., Badaan et al., 2020; Chevrier et al., 2025; Kashima et al., 2025; Wenzel et al., 2024). A key finding across this work is the importance of perceiving future alternatives as both feasible and desirable in order to sustain motivation and engagement (Chevrier et al., 2025; Wenzel et al., 2024). However, these studies typically treat future visions – and their perceived feasibility and desirability – as simply pre-existing cognitive appraisals

that guide action. By contrast, our study provides empirical evidence that both the visions themselves, and the sense of their feasibility and desirability, can emerge *through* action – generated within the unfolding dynamics of collective struggle itself. These findings point to an alternative, yet complementary, perspective: a praxis-based approach that shifts the focus from deliberate envisioning to lived experimentation. In our study, rather than acting on a blueprint, participants came to recognise and enact their desired futures through the collective, transformative practice of resistance. Such a perspective challenges many dominant assumptions in psychological research on social change, which has largely framed collective action as instrumental: a means of securing concessions from power-holders (Clarke & Drury, 2025; Trott, 2016). By contrast, emergent prefiguration suggests collective action can also be valuable as an ‘end in itself’ – involving the emergence and enactment of alternative social forms, even in the absence of a successful outcome.

Thus, as a conceptual lens, emergent prefiguration expands how psychology can understand collective action. By foregrounding praxis as a site of political becoming, our findings call for a psychology that recognises the transformative, future-generating role of resistance. While the ESIM has long recognised struggle as a site where new identities take shape, our findings expand this by suggesting that struggle can also serve as a prefigurative laboratory – a space that can reshape participants’ sense of what futures are possible and worth fighting for.

This praxis-based understanding resonates with long-standing insights from Latin American liberation psychology (e.g., Martín-Baró, 1986), which emphasises praxis as a central site of transformation and collective emancipation. Against individualistic and cognitivist tendencies in Western psychology, thinkers like Martín-Baró (1986) and Freire (1996) argued that critical consciousness and social change emerge not from abstract reasoning, but through the collective experience of resisting oppression – through cycles of collective praxis and critical reflection.

In this light, our study serves as a timely reminder of the importance of developing psychological theory by drawing on experiences and traditions from a broader range of world regions. We hope this work contributes to growing efforts to expand the scope of collective action research—toward a global psychology that is as dynamic and innovative as the movements it seeks to understand.

Conclusion

In this paper, we have explored the emergence of prefigurative collective action in the context of the 2018 Nicaraguan uprising, drawing on in-depth interviews with participants and applying concepts from the ESIM. Through our analysis, we identified four interconnected psychological processes – identity formation, collective self-objectification, empowering outcomes of collective self-objectification, and prefigurative realization – that help explain how resistance can evolve into prefigurative action.

Our findings contribute to the psychological study of prefiguration by demonstrating that prefigurative practices can emerge through struggle itself, rather than stemming from pre-existing ideological commitments. By integrating our empirical insights into an ESIM-based model, we provide a framework for understanding how this dynamic unfolds to be tested and refined in future research.

This study also contributes to broader research on collective action and social change by challenging cognitivist and instrumentalist perspectives that conceptualize protest solely as a tool for achieving policy outcomes, or as driven by pre-existing political visions. Instead, we emphasise struggle as a potentially transformative process, where visions of alternative futures are not only imagined but partially enacted. This praxis-based perspective resonates with insights from Latin American liberation psychology, lending support to growing calls for a more global and dynamic psychology of collective action. At a time of political stagnation and declining trust in traditional institutions, our study underscores collective action as a key resource not only for resisting the world as it is, but also for prefiguring the world that could be.

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